

Preparation of Pre-service and In-service Professional Teacher: BAsed on Intellectual Assessment, Attitude, and Literacy Orientation

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Abstract

The era of communication and global computing needs the presence of professional teachers. Professional teachers who are only based on pedagogical, personal, professional, and social competencies are no longer sufficient. Professional teachers needed now are teachers who have intellectual abilities, ability to behave, and literacy orientation skills. The problem is that in preparing professional teachers, an adequate description of the contribution of the three abilities has not yet been found. This study aims to identify and formulate the preparation of professional teachers through pre-service and in-service pathways based on intellectual ability, attitude ability, and the ability to orient literacy. This study was conducted with a qualitative descriptive approach. It describes and formulates research findings by comparing, conflicting, and contrasting with relevant previous results at the same time, in which this research was carried out until the conclusion stage. The data analysis technique used was descriptive-reflective-holistic (DRH) reinforced with Constant Comparative analysis (CCA) of the Fram Model. The results of the study illustrated that the preparation of professional teachers based on their intellectual abilities, attitude, and the ability of literacy orientation was at 3.52 from the accumulation of grades 4. The average understanding of the code of ethics, exemplary behavior, and literacy abilities in researching the preparation of professional teachers through the PPG pre-service pathway was 3.70, while through the PPG in-service was 3.53. The highest ability possessed by professional teacher candidates was in the attitude of pre-service, with an average value of 3.76. The weakest ability owned by professional teacher candidates was in the second semester in the value of knowledge with an average grade of 3.29. These findings illustrated that the preparation of professional teachers through the PPG pathway was short-term and functioned more for equalization. The professionalism of the code of ethics, exemplary behavior, and literacy ability was precisely determined during the learning process at the sixth level, where study programs completed their undergraduate programs. Therefore, professional teachers needed in the era of communication, and global computing is teachers who always put contextual learning experiences by utilizing their intellectual abilities and attitude to realize the literacy orientation of their students' competence and independence.

Introduction

In the current era, concerning the emerging perceptions of teachers related to the concept of professionalism and professional development activities, some argue that the evidence of professional teachers is to have exemplary attitudes, and have a good attitude in the classroom and outside the classroom (Tanang, 2014, p. 36). For that reason, in improving teacher quality in accordance with its substance, professional teachers themselves must pay attention to the four competency frameworks. A collaborative process can be evidence of improved teaching (Gore, 2017, p. 112). However, what is happening right now is that there is a lot of concerns for the teachers who are holding off their creativity. The cause is a guarantee of life (Spratt, 2018, p. 137).

Professionalism comes from the word profession. Mc Cully defines the profession as "a vocation in which the professed knowledge of some departments of learning or science is used in its application to

the affairs of others or the practice of an art founded upon it." The problem that is happening right now is the amount of unconsciousness experienced by teachers or teacher candidates regarding professionalism. There are professional and competency components that must be possessed because these elements lead them to the future and the seriousness of their entire teaching careers (Trif, 2013, p. 230).

Therefore, teacher leadership must have an orientation toward clear goals. The tendency to consume research, curriculum understanding with a vision of school development, high-quality teaching, and being able to work collaboratively with other teachers, is a critical reflection and important research orientation on teacher professionalism (Niemi, 2015, p. 291).

With the pre-service program, it is welcomed by pre-service teachers because they think positively about the program. Conceptual thinking that is implanted is the self-representatives of future teachers. Therefore, the teacher's identity is dynamic. The teacher educators and tutors are not worried about this, but the biggest challenge for them is the complexity of the course and the placement of the field to maintain enthusiasm as a professional teacher and strong identity (Beltman, 2015, p. 241). What actually happens is that this teacher education program has good intentions and prepares high-quality teachers for teenagers today. If seen from the adolescents, there are many talented people, but many do not have education according to national opportunities yet, due to the lack of training for the teachers to determine their characteristics (Bagel, 2006, p. 357).

To strengthen a teacher who has a high professional, which must be underlined, is the administration that must be addressed, and the school of education must specify a teacher specialist. Professionalism indirectly shows aspects that affect the performance of school education; what should be paid attention to is diversity, interactivity, and results-oriented learning (Xeinsi, 2016, p. 29). A salient finding from a research on professionalism conducted by Darmadi (2015: 162) is that more attention should be given to teachers. As Darmadi states, teachers have roles, duties, competencies and responsibilities towards their students and these roles cannot be replaced by any elements, not even by a sophisticated machine. This teacher preparation program by explicitly conceptualizing the activities is carried out; thus, practical thinking about what is on the ground will be better when it is realized (Skerrett, 2015, p. 598). The ability to think about aspects of the teacher's professional vision in classroom situations is important and is seen as the initial key to teacher education. The aspect of professional vision is to describe, explain, and predict classrooms (Sturmer, 2015, p. 123).

Materials and Method

This research was qualitative descriptive research. Qualitative research is research that is used to describe or answer the problems of a phenomenon or event that is happening right now, both about phenomena in a single variable, or correlation and/or comparison of various variables (Arifin, 2011, p. 54). Phenomenology research tries to explain or uncover the meaning of the concept of the phenomenon of experience based on the consciousness that occurs in some individuals. This research was conducted in a natural situation, so there were no limits in interpreting or understanding the phenomenon being studied. According to Creswell, 2015, p. 54), the phenomenological approach postpones all judgments about natural attitudes until a certain basis is found. This delay is usually called an *epoche* (time period). The concept of *epoche* is to distinguish data areas (subjects) from the interpretations of researchers. The *epoche* concept becomes the center where the researcher compiles and classifies initial assumptions about phenomena to understand what is said by respondents. Research to be conducted by researchers was a qualitative phenomenological study. The main problem discussed in this study was to analyze several articles related to teacher professional education. Qualitative data analysis techniques in the analysis activities were carried out interactively and directly to the end until the data was saturated. Data analysis included reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing/verification (Moleong Lexy j, 2017, p. 248). Data were collected using the instrument in the form of a questionnaire. For the first questionnaire about intellectual understanding, it consisted of 26 items. The second questionnaire about the understanding of attitude consisted of 24 items. The third questionnaire concerning understanding orientation consisted of 24 items. In this case, the questionnaire contained four competencies that must be possessed by professional teachers. The answers were in the form of a Likert scale with a score of 1 to 4 in a row, expressing very less knowledge to very sufficient knowledge.

Results and Discussion

Results

This research was conducted among students of the Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta as the data source. Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta this year was mandated by the Ministry of Research, Technology, and Higher Education to conduct PPG program activities. Requirements for Educational Personnel Organizations (LPTKs) as PPG implementing agencies already have the terms and conditions listed in the National Accreditation Board for Higher Education (BAN-PT). These requirements are in the form of commitment to the

ESPBED report and field verification to check the suitability of PPG organizer proposals. The contents of the proposal are in the form of human resource qualifications (HR), the quality of facilities, and targets according to the *tridarma* (three obligations) of tertiary institutions that support education programs and field experience programs.

Seeing the conditions that currently coincide with the PPG program activities, the object of this research was PPG students and PGSD students. The researcher took the source of data from the preparation of professional teachers, among PPG pre-service students, in-service, PGSD students in semester 2, 4, and 6. In this case, PPG students should participate directly in this research because this research would map the ability of professional teachers in terms of intellectual assessment, attitudes, and orientation. How much PPG students understand that they have gained from their experiences. Therefore, whether the experience they have gained was in accordance with what they have already had. PGSD of semester 2, 4, and 6 students were teacher candidates. For that reason, they have already had maturity in thinking, and what they got in college was in accordance with what they wanted relating to the development of professional teachers. Therefore, they should have the ability to increase each year individually for the sustainability of educators in educating prospective educators.

In the discussion about this professional teacher, there were three questionnaires given to respondents whose numbers were 445. They consisted of 27 people in semester 2, 15 people in semester 4, 67 people in semester 6, 38 people in pre-service, and 298 people in in-services, to find out how far their understanding. The first questionnaire was about intellectual understanding. The second questionnaire was about understanding attitudes, and the third questionnaire was about understanding orientation. In this case, the questionnaire contained four competencies that should be possessed by professional teachers. Basically, the questionnaire was grouped according to their respective titles. For intellectual questionnaires, it was to test their intellectual understanding, how much experience did they have in terms of knowledge. For the attitude understanding questionnaire, it tried to reflect on whether what has been done every day or the activities carried out every day were in accordance with the criteria they naturally did. It was because professional teachers are educating to hone themselves and set an example, and the rest is compassion. The orientation understanding questionnaire was about how they applied the understanding they have gained during their studies. Latygovskaya (2015: 377) states that in the process of professionalization, identification and formation of personal ability and quality of the subject of professional activities can and should be used for a successful career and potential development, such as communicative, productive, and axiological. The application was indeed the final stage of everything, how they became useful or shared their knowledge with students. Quite often, there were still lacking in terms of application. The factors vary, but it is not a drawback that must be a problem because the experience that has been done is far more important than everything.

Orientation Skills of Level 6 Professional Teacher Candidates at the Bachelor of Education Level

Figure 1.

Nilai orientasi: Orientation value
Nilai sikap: Attitude value
Nilai intelektual: Intellectual value

The results of mapping per semester above, the three higher grades were semester 4, and the lowest was semester 2. Because in semester 4, students still felt pleasure in the world of learning, and there were not too many demands for what kind of professional teacher candidates. In the 6th semester, students began to look forward and thought again what kind of professional teacher they would be in the future. One's professional behavior is related to professional ethics that can influence others, the existence of judgments that are based on individual, social, cultural, and professionalism. In the end, human values determine one's ethics. It is influenced by a profession that will belong to someone, but actions and behavior are one's own (Jackson, 2013, p. 123). The existence of diverse individual, social, and cultural influenced students who had different levels; these factors

affected their thinking patterns. In critical thinking skills, a person has a basis in the form of interpretation, problem discovery, observation, and flexible thinking. These sections influence someone in critical thinking to form a particular design or goal that he wants (Bowen, 2013, p. 421).

The existence of critical thinking that is influenced by several factors also affects a person's behavior. Several factors influenced a student's confidence to get specific values and goals they wanted to get. There were implicit intelligence and relevance that was felt by students who were focused on student performance. In this case, there is an experiment that they experienced or an event that has been experienced, and they analyze it themselves to develop critical thinking (Miele, 2014, p. 533). Students who demonstrate the ability to think critically in analyzing an event, they can determine, evaluate, and plan the goals they want.

Intellectual Ability, Attitude, and Orientation of Professional Teacher Candidates Based on Level 6-7

Figure 2.
Nilai orientasi: Orientation value
Nilai sikap: Attitude value
Nilai intelektual: Intellectual value
Pra-jabatan: pre-service
Dalam jabatan: in-service

Pre-service participants excelled in the assessment of attitude and orientation, meaning that participants in this position were more likely to have good attitudes and orientations because they still believed in enthusiasm for work and creativity. It is natural because they were still fresh (fresh graduates). However, in-service participants had more experience or intellectual experience. However, unfortunately, in its application, in-service tended to be relatively low. Therefore, the assessment of attitudes and orientation of in-service was quite low compared to pre-services. Professionalism and ethics are challenges now, both of which get a rating system. There is progressiveness for curriculum development and assessment practices that are explicit in achievement. In this case, there is a need for more interactive educational techniques to try out their role in professionalism in professional education (Kelly, 2019, p. 8). Therefore, in this program, there should be an increase in intellectual, attitudes, and orientation, which pre-service instincts have been increasingly developing their creative instincts, and in-service were aware of the creativity they had. In this case, the teacher's approach was very influential on the creativity of students, which is basically, a teacher must have the creativity to support students in learning. There is a need for teaching concepts that take the initiative to build creativity, and the awareness of teachers that must be possessed (Ott, 2010, p. 166). Creativity is needed by professional teachers who are not only competent in knowledge but also have good outcomes in creating creativity in learning. Creativity is not a difficult thing to do, but some people do not have confidence. Though everyone can be creative, everyone learns in their way. The needs of each student are continually adjusting throughout the project work (Drelinga, 2015, p. 209). Training students is to build creativity, and teachers are not instructors who only tell to be creative, but what should be is the teacher guides students to be creative.

Intellectual Ability, Attitude, and Orientation of Professional Teacher Candidates Based on Semester Level 6 with Level 7 of Pre-service PPG

Figure 3.
Nilai orientasi: Orientation value
Nilai sikap: Attitude value
Nilai intelektual: Intellectual value
Semester 6: Sixth Semester
Pra-jabatan: pre-service

In essence, pre-service was dominant towards the three assessments above, because the hard times have passed, had more experience, and had higher professionalism. Experienced teachers have a deeper understanding of competence in helping to achieve the maximum quality of one's professional work. It takes a long time to become an expert teacher (Okas, 2014, p. 342). Therefore, experience and education are essential for teacher candidates; the existence of extensive knowledge has an impact on learning. It is strange if teachers do not have broad insights because the need for extensive knowledge is to create quality teaching. In the thought of the faction, whose contents are about the design of educational programs, adequate knowledge is needed to make it look systematic in compiling it. In this case, knowledge and experience can illustrate that they learn about the ways the teachers learn and how educators influence learning (Beswecik, 2018, p. 204). Knowledge and experience are the primary targets in terms of learning, where teachers are creative in accordance with what they had previously gotten, felt, and done alone. There is a situation that illustrates that professional teachers can change from the start of their characteristics and identities, starting from their experience being updated by their professional environment. In this case, for a person who works in a professional environment, there is a significant increase in the effect of accumulation in his professional career (Papay, 2014, p. 495). The influence of one's environment can be useful knowledge because of the learning that results from the experience they do. A person's experience becomes learning for others that have never been done.

Discussion

If all of them were classified, the in-service PPG intellectual value was superior to other levels. However, for the value of attitude and orientation, the pre-service PPG was superior. It is not strange to predict that the intellectual superior was the one who has been engaged in education for a long time but only lacked in its application. Whereas, for the pre-service, they only lacked in intellectual, for its implementation, it was in line with what was expected. As explained by Weber (87: 2012), only through the guidance of professional teachers every student can become a quality, competitive, and productive human resource as a national asset to face the increasingly tight competition at present and in the future. As a result, all teachers must realize that they are required to become professional teachers for the betterment of themselves, students, education and the nation. Experienced teachers tended to take shortcuts to facilitate learning. The facility is defined as power. There is no truth besides the facility. Memorization and copying were the results of the facilities used. Inexperienced teachers tended to provide the space needed to build professional expertise (Rodrigues, 2018, p. 151). The experience here tended to be felt negatively if not used, but if it were used, it would be felt positively. It encourages the experience that should be used properly. A teacher is a person who educates the next generation, so that knowledge which is in line with its application is needed. Not because who is the most experienced, but who can best share the experience in real form. The knowledge possessed by professional teachers is not only in practical manifestations, namely the classroom. It is necessary to master the content that is observed and presented through the knowledge shown about the subject's contents and the way the teacher does it to clarify doubts. Their skills and knowledge enable them to deliver teaching satisfaction better (Marli, 2013, p. 809). Engaging learning is learning that gives meaning and satisfaction to the students to be more motivating in learning. Teachers should at least have the skills or expertise in the form of knowledge and counseling. Both knowledge is needed in the

learning process. There is the fact that it is relatively important. There is a need to increase understanding and strengthen content about experimental teaching and curriculum content system (Kang, 2009, p. 589). The skills and expertise should be possessed by both teachers and teacher candidates, in which these skills indeed become their superiority and will be shared with students. It is in line with Santos' statement (2015: 173) that this Professional Education Policy is made to create a balance with other professions because there are no further or sustainable programs to confirm or declare that a teacher has become an expert in their field

Conclusion

Professional teachers must have a wealth of experience, in terms of knowledge that plays a role in understanding the prevailing professional code of ethics, as well as insights about education. Imaniyati (2017: 102) teachers who have competencies will be more qualified in the learning process inside and outside the classroom. The attitude of the professional teacher must set a good example for his students, so that students emulate good ones too. Therefore, orientation in becoming a professional teacher must be well-formed. It is by frequently researching to know the current problems and what solutions must be done. Alibakhshi (2015) thus, teachers should bear it in mind that professional development is no longer an obligation but a need of teachers. With the existence of a teacher professional education program, it can hone intellectual abilities, attitudes, and proper orientation to become a truly professional teacher. The experience gained in the program has positive results, but after completing the program, teacher candidates should be aware of what they have learned and have their provisions.

Teachers who have good intellectual do not necessarily have good attitudes and orientations. Likewise, for the other components, if one of them is sufficient, but the other components are lacking, then there is less harmony. These components are interrelated with one another. Therefore, teacher candidates should pay attention and understand well, what they have to do properly, and if they want to become a professional teacher.

This research could be a reference material for teacher training colleges as a future evaluation material to form a professional teacher. There needs awareness from a teacher to increase his potential to become a professional teacher to educate and guide students to become the best generation of the nation.

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References

- Alibakhshi, Goudarz & Dehvari, N. (2015). "EFL Teachers Perception of Continuing Professional Development". A Case of Iranian High School Teachers. <http://ax.doi.org/10-15446/profile>. Vol.17, No.2. Bogota. Colombia
- Arifin. 2010. *Metode penelitian kualitatif, kuantitatif, dan R & D*. Bandung: Alfabeta
- Beltman, S., Glass, C., Dinham, J., Chalk, B., & Nguyen, B. (2015). Drawing identity: Beginning pre-service teachers' professional identities. *Issues in Educational Research*, 25(3), 225–245.
- Bowen, D. H., Greene, J. P., & Kisida, B. (2013). Learning to Think Critically. *Educational Researcher*, 43(1), 37–44. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189x13512675>
- Creswell, John W. 2015. *Penelitian Kualitatif & Desain Riset*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- Darmadi, Hamid. (2015). Duties, Roles, Competencies, and Responsibilities of Professional Teachers. Pontianak: *Journal of Education*, Vol. 13, No. 2.
- Drelinga, E. (2005). *Skolot Ā Ju Un Jaun Ā Ko Klašu Skol Ē Nu Sadarb Ī Ba P Ē Tniecisko Prasmju Veidošan Ā S ProceĀ Teacher-learner Cooperation to Develop Research Skills in Lower Elementary School Ievads*. I, 203–210.
- Fram, S. M. (2013). The constant comparative analysis method outside of grounded theory. *Qualitative Report*, 18(1), 1–25.
- Gore, J., Lloyd, A., Smith, M., Bowe, J., Ellis, H., & Lubans, D. (2017). Effects of professional development on the quality of teaching: Results from a randomised controlled trial of Quality Teaching Rounds. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 68, 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.08.007>
- Imaniyati, Nani, & Ayu D. K. P. 2017. Teacher Professional Development in Improving Teacher Performance. *Journal of Office Management Education*. 1 (1): 103
- Jackson, C. I. (2013). Professionalism, Ethics, and Legal Issues. 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-384727-0.00012-4>
- Kang, K. H. (2009). Analysis Of Difficulties Experienced By Pre-Serservice Secondary Science Teachers In Student- Teacher Practice
- Kelly, A. M., & Mullan, P. B. (n.d.). Designing a Curriculum for Professionalism and Ethics Within Radiology: *Academic Radiology*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acra.2018.02.007>

- Latygovskaya, T., Bukharina, Z., & Chubik, A. (2015). Professionalism as a Generalized Typical Model of a Professional in the Higher Education System. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 206(November), 374–377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.10.068>.
- Maleong, Lexy. J. 2017. *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya
- Marli, V., Backes, S., Luis, J., Moya, M., Lenise, M., & Carmo, J. (2013). Expressions Of Pedagogical Content Knowledge Of An Expressões Do Conhecimento Pedagógico Do Conteúdo De. 22(3), 804–810
- Miele, D. B., & Wigfield, A. (2014). Quantitative and Qualitative Relations Between Motivation and Critical-Analytic Thinking. *Educational Psychology Review*, 26(4), 519–541. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-014-9282-2>
- Niemi, H. (2015). Teacher Professional Development in Finland: *Towards a More Holistic Approach*. 7(3), 279–294.
- Okas, A., van der Schaaf, M., & Krull, E. (2014). Novice and experienced teachers' views on professionalism. *Trames*, 18(4), 327–344. <https://doi.org/10.3176/tr.2014.4.02>
- Ott, M., Pozzi, F., & Tavella, M. (2010). Teacher, what do you mean by “creativity”? An Italian survey on the use of ICT to foster student creativity. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, 111 CCIS (PART 1), 165–171. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16318-0_19
- Papay, J. P. (2014). Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis Returns to Teaching Experience. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0162373713519496>
- Rodrigues, L. de A. D., de Pietri, E., Sanchez, H. S., & Kuchah, K. (2018). The role of experienced teachers in the development of pre-service language teachers' professional identity: Revisiting school memories and constructing future teacher selves. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 88(October 2017), 146–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2018.02.002>.
- Santos, Sheila D. M. D. (2015). Teacher training policies for professional education: *conflicts and permanence marked by the neoliberal ideology*. *Maringá*. 37(2):173.
- Skerrett, A., & Williamson, T. (2015). Reconceptualizing Professional Communities for Preservice Urban Teachers. *The Urban Review*, 47(4), 579–600. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11256-015-0325-x>
- Sprott, R. A. (2019). Factors that foster and deter advanced teachers' professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 77, 321–331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.11.001>
- Stürmer, K., Seidel, T., & Holzberger, D. (2016). Intra-individual differences in developing professional vision: preservice teachers' changes in the course of an innovative teacher education program. *Instructional Science*, 44(3), 293–309. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-016-9373-1>
- Tanang, H., & Abu, B. (2014). Teacher Professionalism and Professional Development Practices in South Sulawesi, Indonesia. 3(2), 25–42. <https://doi.org/10.5430/jct.v3n2p25>
- Trif, L., & Popescu, T. (2013). Pre-service Teacher Trainees' Perceptions of Professional Development. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 76, 816–820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.04.212>
- Weber, C. L., & Johnsen, S. K. (2012). Teacher Professionalism. *Gifted Child Today*, 35(1), 5–5. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1076217511429676>

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